

A TENTATIVE SCENARIO OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN URBAN AND PER-URBAN AREA OF KHULNA DISTRICT THROUGH THE RESOURCE REUSE

Sharfan Upaul¹ SK Farjana Faruk Nitu²,

¹Lecturer, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Khulna, Bangladesh. Email: s.upaul@urp.kuet.ac.bd

Arpita Bakshi³

^{2,3}Undergraduate Student, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET), Khulna, Bangladesh. Email: farjana.urp42@gmail.com² and arpitabakshi36@gmail.com³

ABSTRACT

As a developing country of Bangladesh, budding urbanization affects badly in the environment because of the mismanagement of solid waste. This research focuses on the waste stream management disparity between the perspectives of urban as Khulna city corporation area and peri-urban area as Paikgachha Upazila, Khulna. The study also introduces the economical way of resource recovery by reuse. Almost 300 native and key stakeholders have been surveyed randomly to collect the primary data (i.e., socio-economic characteristics of respondents, perception and attitude of the respondents, etc.). Secondary data (i.e., population, waste generation and types etc.) have been collected from past researches. T test, severity index (SI) has been adopted to show the consciousness of respondents about waste management. The environmental impacts of the four waste management scenarios were also determined. In the future, this research will help to decide to invest in a particular area of better waste management.

KEYWORD: Solid waste generation, Solid waste reuse, Khulna City, Peri-urban Area.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last several decades, the issues associated with the management of municipal solid waste (MSW) have acquired a disturbing dimension in developing countries. Besides, the tremendous urbanization and population growth have become an important issue in managing those urban waste by increasing economic activities (Ahsan et al., 2014; Belboom et al., 2013). However, the per capita production of solid waste in urban residential areas is much lower in developing countries compared to developed countries, the ability of developing countries to collect, manage, dispose or reuse solid waste in a cost-effective manner is significantly restricted compared to developed countries (Tchobanoglous, Hilary, & Samuel, 1993). The solid waste management system in Bangladesh is currently not well-organized and focuses mainly on collection and disposing.

Khulna is the third biggest metropolitan, commercial, industrial and port city with a population of 1.13 million and an area of 45 square kilometers in Bangladesh (BBS, 2011). The solid waste collection,

transportation, distribution and treatment in Khulna District confide on Khulna City Corporation (KCC), pursuant to the KCC Ordinance, 1984 ignoring recycling and composting (Murtaza, 2002). The waste generation rate is already 0.50 kg/cap/day in 950 tons of garbage as a whole and huge amount of waste is uncollected (Riyad & Farid, 2014). Wastes are usually stored either by the citizens themselves or community-based organizations or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) via their door-to-door waste collection system in the community bins and secondary transfer stations (STS) (Alamin & Hasan, 2013). Moreover, these uncollected wastes are deposited in open fields, streets and drains, obstructing the drainage system, resulting in significant environmental pollution and health care.

As per study, there have seldom any research that evaluate the tentative scenario of waste collection and management in both the urban and peri-urban areas of Khulna district. This paper aims to constructive differentiation between paikgacha (as peri-urban area) and KCC area (as urban area) in the context of current waste stream management and endeavor to introduces the strategy and upgrade technology of resource recovery by recycling involving impact assessment of environment.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Selection of Study Area

Khulna is the third largest city of Bangladesh surrounded in the south by Jessore and Narail, west of Bagerhat, east of Satkhira, and north of the Bay of Bengal within the latitude and longitude of 22.84628°

Figure 1: Map of the study area (KCC and Paikgacha) (Source: Author, 2020)

N, 89.53832° E. The total area of the town is measured at 45.65 km² with a population of 1.5 million (KCC, 2017). Several sites were chosen to assess the quantity of waste handled and to understand the current waste management scenario: KCC for delineating urban scenario and Paikgacha Upazila as peri-urban aspects.

Data Collection and analyzing

The primary data were collected mainly using Questionnaire survey by the interrogation of local people of the urban and peri-urban area (Table 1). As the population was known, finite sample size was estimated for sampling. But so far limitation, 300 native stakeholders was selected within random sampling. 150 household was taken from KCC and 150 household was selected from peri-urban (Paikgacha upazila, Khulna). Socio economic characteristics refers to a great correlation to the waste management practices. Socio economic variable (family size, education qualification, average monthly income) was mentioned within percentage. Estimation of collective solid waste like as vegetable, food,

plastic, paper, glass, wood, metal, leather) generation rate (ton/month) was calculated by the projection of previous years (2016 & 2017) data. Waste collection section (pick up from home, fixed pickup point, no waste collection) was analyzed from both of urban and peri-urban respondent percentage. To assess of waste recyclable process (generation, recycled, recycled rate, and contribution to reduction) was represented from two context stakeholder's response. Solid waste treatment practices (composting, burning, open dumping, unsanitary landfill, incineration WTE) was valuation from participant % of answer. All these types of variable play a significant role to identify the disparity between urban and peri-urban context. T-statistics was used to analyze the factors (House size, income level, and extra land, environment consciousness, willing to separate the waste) that was affected waste generation. Severity index (%) was used through the response of people to show the consciousness of respondents about waste management. From this, the inequality of consciousness towards waste management between two dimensions was disclosed. The weighted comparison between urban and peri-urban respondents' opinions (activities of waste collection, status of the current storage equipment, Frequency of waste collection, Reasons for not applying composting, Reasons for not recycling, Households' view of the factors contributing to the improvement of SWM system, Types of materials that are separated by families etc.) Was symbolized by using graph.

ANALYSIS

Amongst the surveyed data male and female ratio were almost close (37:46) and join family (>8 persons) was the lowest in number (23 %). The higher educated and income persons were lowest in portion (9% and 16% respectively). The estimation of waste generation is attained by the help of projection system within the waste generation data of 2016 and 2017. Among the different types of solid waste, the vegetable and foods section reflect the high weight in two contexts. Others MSW perspective in peri-urban area, here exist a less amount to the compare of urban area (table 1).

Table 01: Estimate of waste generation (ton/month)

MSW Components	Urban (KCC)	Peri-urban (Paikgaccha upazilla)
Foods & vegetables	10656.39	1598.35
Plastic	418.69	62.79
Paper	1283.09	192.45
Glass	67.53	10.12
Metal & Tin	148.57	22.28
Dust, Ash, Soil	499.73	74.95
Brick, Concrete & Stone	148.56	22.28
Textile & Woods	175.58	26.33
Rubber & Leather	67.53	10.12
Others	162.07	24.30
Total	13506.201	2034.97

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

In between two contexts, a huge dissimilarity is represented towards the waste collection process (table 2). Among all respondent of peri-urban area, 22% respondent was claimed that, there was no waste collection process.

Table 02: Estimate of waste collection process weekly (% Response from two context)

Area	Pick up from home (KCC/legal authority)	Fixed pickup point (KCC/legal authority)	Pick from home (privately)	Fixed pickup point((privately)	No waste collection process (dumped in open place/pond)
Urban	15%	55%	25%	5%	0%
Peri-urban	0%	56%	7%	15%	22%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

That's why they were obliged to use open place or pond as solid waste management place. Overall, 100% area was not covered in the services of waste collection in fixed pickup point by legal authority. Also pick up from home services was 0% from the stakeholder response that was burden of them.

Table 03: Estimate of recyclable waste (ton/month) (Response from two context)

Material	Generation of recyclables		Estimated recycled waste		Recycle rate (%)		Contribution to waste reduction(comment)	
	Urban	Peri-urban	Urban	Peri-urban	Urban	Peri-urban	Urban	Peri-urban
Plastic	0.035	0.028	0.023	0.014	63%	50%	Very Good	Good
Paper	0.130	0.100	0.006	0.040	50%	40%	Good	Bad
Glass	0.006	0.004	0.003	0.002	50%	50%	Good	Good
Metal	0.016	0.012	0.012	0.004	75%	33%	Very Good	Very Bad
Textile & Woods	0.015	0.015	0.009	0.007	60%	48%	Very good	Bad
Others	0.028	0.013	0.150	0.005	52%	39%	Good	Very bad
Total	0.230	0.170	0.260	0.072	53%	43%	Good	Bad

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 3 represents the amount of waste in ton per month that can be recycled or reused rather than direct through away. These data show the assumption base amount got from the users. Among the data it can be found that metal has the highest probability to get recycled along with the plastic and textiles elements. The possible cause is metal and textile goods can reuse with some minor treatment. Table 4 represents treatment practice of solid waste for both regions. In both cases open dumping is dominant but for peri urban area people practice the burning methods rather than composting as lack of improved management.

Table 04: solid Waste treatment practices (% Response from two context)

Area	Composting (%)	Burning (%)	Open dumping (%)	Unsanitary landfilling (%)	Incineration of WTE (%)
Urban	8%	12%	70%	10%	0%
Peri urban	0%	25%	55%	20%	0%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

From figure 2, peri-urban area is far away from the urban area in waste collection and the frequency of it. The urban area has city corporation authority who manages the collection system better than the peri-urban government. Most of the common people think the authority has that kind of ability to recycle the waste lack of awareness and interest it is still very low in city corporation area as a result most of the recyclable waste mixed with the other septic waste. Again, most of the people think the government can improve the SWM system by improving the logistical support and technology than it giving to the private sector.

In table 5 several factors have been shown as how they influence the waste generation practices. The table shows that age has no certain effect that match the reality. Waste generated by the household not the age in direct, moreover, the household size is also insignificant here. Among all the income group and consciousness are significant in this case. The possible cause may be more educated household has the average income who are conscious in waste generation.

Fig 02: Tentative Comparison of Urban and Peri-urban Respondents' Opinion towards Solid Waste

a) Respondents' opinions on the activities of waste collection b) Frequency of waste collection service (as per the respondents) c) Reasons for not recycling waste materials d) Dealing with recyclable materials in neighborhoods g) Households' view of the factors contributing to the improvement of SWM system i) the response that influence the household towards the waste management.

Table 05: Factors affecting waste generations [^{*}significant at P≤.05***Significant at p≤ 0.01]

Variables	Estimation	Standard error	t-statistics
Age			
15-25 years (Age1)	-0.14	0.11	-1.27
26-40years (Age2)	0.12	0.18	0.98
Income			
Lower income (Income 1)	0.08	0.34	0.24
Middle income (Income 2)	0.89	0.22	7.78***
Household size	0.58	0.44	2.22
Willing to separate the waste	0.64	0.18	2.78*
Extra land	0.09	1.68	0.08
Environment consciousness	0.72	0.18	4.50***

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

The field survey shows that at various locations in Khulna area, there are 17 small hauled container points SHCPs, 26 large LHCPs, 12 Distinct collection Routes (DCR) and 11 Solid disposal Sites (STS) which collected and transported MSW 375ton per day. The mean distance driven by the KCC collection trucks was approximately 2162.3 km/day for this garbage collection and landfilling purpose. And the diesel fuel efficiency of collection truck was 2.25 km/L and 2.5 km/L for transportation truck. In addition, 37.20 tons of solid waste per day in Khulna is recycled by the private sector (Moniruzzaman et al., 2011) and Composted MSW was 18 ton/day. The quantity of MSW handled by landfilling in FDS is therefore 356 t d-1.

Table 6: Present practice of solid waste management in Khulna city by KCC

Name of the sites	Average Quantity of MSW (t d-1)	Total
Secondary disposal sites	184	375 ton/day
Large hauled container points	99.8	
Small hauled container points	15.9	
Distinct collection routes	75.3	

(Source: KCC data projection, 2017)

PROPOSAL OF COMPRESSIVE SWM and EASY ECONOMICAL REUSEOF VARIOUS SOLID WASTE

The Table 7 offers an overview of four model scenarios in Khulna City for a comprehensive solid waste management (SWM) abstracted from the past researche (Islam & Moniruzzam, 2019). In the current practice of KCC was considered as baseline situation(S-0) where the recycling and composting percentage is negligible and very high the landfilling percentage. Composting is increased in scenario 1 (S-1) (26.3 percent), recycling is considered to be the same as baseline scenario (9.20 percent) and landfilling was reduced (64.6 percent). In the second scenario, it is possible to get alternative fuels by combusting non-recyclable plastic, paper, labels and many corrugated materials by obtaining Refuse-Derived fuel (RDF) incineration. In S-2 scenario, there have also increased composting process and Landfilling is declined. But by generating incineration process, these MSW can be reduced as a greater percentage and also produce electricity by these wastes. In the Asian developing countries like ours adopt incineration as it has the capacity of treat up to 2000 ton waste daily(tpd) (Aleluia & Ferrão, 2017). Therefore, in the scenario 3, the landfilling is tremendously reduced by introducing incineration and remain composting as same as baseline situation. But conducting so much incineration hampers the environmental viability as per cause various contamination of earth. And immense use of composting can impair the soli quality. So, the scenario-4 is the combination of incineration (36.8%) and composting (54.7%) maintains the balance of environment and manage the waste at a great extent.

Table 7: Depiction of modelled scenarios

Modelled scenarios	Recycling (%)	Composting (%)	Landfilling (%)
Baseline scenario (S-0)	9.20	4.3	86.5
Scenario 1 (S-1)	9.20	26.3	64.6
Scenario 2 (S-2)	13.6	32.7	46.3
Scenario 3 (S-3)	71.0	4.3	24.7
Scenario 4 (S-4)	36.8	54.7	8.50

Plastic and Polythene Reuse

By making a DIY plastic bottle planter and laundry detergent bottles into a watering can. Besides a milk carton can be transform into a garden scooper. A piggy bank can be created from a reusable plastic bottle. Reusing can be done by honey bear bottles by creating a lamp. Beach bucket from laundry detergent cans and plastic bottle waste into a trash can also be a modern practice. Developing the outdoor broom from recycled plastic bottles and reuse soda bottles by making a vertical garden can also be the fruitful reuse of it ([Mansour & Mansour, 2015](#)). A Model of Polythene Recycling Machine for Pollution Control Economic Development in Nigeria ([Ikechukwu & IAENG, 2013](#)).It can be a great opportunity for developing country because of it's an easy and economical way.

Paper, Glass and Wood Reuse

Papier Mache decoration pieces and tray, newspaper baskets, picture frames of recycled paper can be some smart use of paper. Besides, recycled paper bags, bookmarks of recycled ice cream sticks, recycled paper wall hangings, and recycled paper bracelets are also some modern use that can be recommended ([Rajput, Bhagade, Raut, Ralegaonkar, & Mandavgane, 2012](#)). Again, DIY liquid soap dispenser, safe spray bottle can be made by using the used glass. Glass can be reuse in home decoration such as: handmade holiday decorations, up cycled lantern, up cycled oil lamp, gorgeous bottle tree, self-watering herb garden, custom pincushion, adorable candy jars ([Colombo, Brusatin, Bernardo, & Scarinci, 2003](#)). Old pallets of wood can be turned into ideal rustic planter boxes, pallet swing, kitchen island, arrange your kitchen with a rustic pallet spice rack. The wood can be reused on other home accessories making.

Metal and Tire reuse

Washing machine drum can be turned into a chair and washing tub can be turned into a picture shelf frame. Old metal bucket can be turned into a lamp and old metal wheel can be turned into a patio art window. Picture frame can also be built of old barbwire. Again, recycled oil drum can be turned into a cushioned bench, sewing machine stand can be made into a planter ([RemoveandReplace, 2015](#)). Tire can be used on decoration purposes, such as: tire mirror frame, lovely tire and yarn planter along with the garden tire bench, tire subwoofer, tire garden steps, tire armchair, half tire hammocks, tire tea cup planters. Besides, tire garden planter, installation of green city tiers, outdoor tire furniture can be made from the used tires.

Vegetation Food and Leather Reuse

Recycling of food waste to produce the plant fertilizer ([Ahmed & Abdulla , 2018](#)). Cheap and durable leather belt camera strap can be made from leather reusing. Again, leather belt message board can be reproduced. Some other cool products such as: cool leather belt door mat, elegant clock hanger, DIY angling terrarium, antique belt wrapped vase, DIY leather belt crate, DIY leather shelf show rage, drawer pulls of DIY leather can be made by reusing the leather ([Ammasi, Victor, Chellan, & Chellappa, 2019](#)) .

DISCUSSION

A massive dissimilarity in the aspect of waste generation, waste collection system, recycle rate, waste treatment process also in the perception of general people was signified within the compare of urban (KCC) and per-urban (Paikgaccha upazilla, Khulna) zone. As urban area is mostly covered with commercial and industrial area with rapid urbanization, the waste generation rate was tremendous that

estimated total 13506 (ton/month) by projection of waste generation data 2016 and 2017. In the other aspect of the peri-urban area, for total number of populations 225089, the specific category solid waste (plastic, paper, glasses, metal, tin, dust of soil-brick, concrete, stone, textile, wood, rubber, leather, others) estimation rate 2034.97 (tons/month). In section of waste collection system, huge disparity was disclosed. Generally, 22% of stakeholders were not receive the services area in peri-urban but another perspective in urban area none respondent was existed without waste collection services. Fixed pick-up point was the common services that was mostly available (urban-56%, peri-urban-55%). For 150 respondent, generation of recyclable rate (ton/month), estimated recycled waste, recycle rate of (%) in urban area were 0.23, 0.26, and 53% also in peri-urban area were 0.17, .072, and 43% respectively. The assessment of contribution towards waste reduction was urban area was favorable but another dimension was worst. In peri-urban area, 25% people was responded burning to the waste treatment but less amount of people (12%) was used to the burning process. Open dumping was the common scenario in both of area (urban-70%, peri-urban-55%). T-test for factors affecting waste generations, highly ***Significant at $p \leq 0.01$ value was (middle income 7.78, environment consciousness 4.50) and 'significant at $P \leq 0.05$ was willing to separate waste 2.78. Tentative Comparison graph of urban and peri-urban respondents' particular opinion towards solid waste goes to majority that they do not know how to recycle and good accessibility to logistic support for proper waste management.

CONCLUSION

In the sense of current waste stream management, this paper aims at a positive distinction between Paikgacha (as a peri-urban area) and KCC area (as an urban area) and depict a future sustainable solid management scenario for concerned areas. In this respect, a variety of field surveys have been performed. The severity indicates the consciousness of waste management among respondents in both urban and peri urban areas with some driving factors related to waste disposal behavior of residents. Besides, considering different proportions of recycling and composting, four waste management scenarios were created. The following are the key conclusions taken from the present study:

- 1) Foods and paper related waste is predominately making mess according to future solid waste generation estimation.
- 2) The consciousness of residents in accordance with waste management are eminent in urban area compared to peri-urban area.
- 3) Among the four-waste management scenario, the combination of incineration and composting balance environmental viability and manage waste in both Urban and peri-urban area.
- 4) Government has the ability, just need the logistical improvements and take the action.

References

- Afroz, R., & Tudin, R. (2014). Selected socio-economic factors affecting the willingness to minimise solid waste in Dhaka city, Bangladesh. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 1-23.
- Ahmed, R. R., & Abdulla, A. I. (2018). Recycling of Food Waste to Produce the Plant Fertilizer. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 1-6.
- Alamgir, M., McDonald, C., Roehl, K. E., & Ahsan, M. (2005). Present Scenario of Municipal Solid Waste and its Management: Chapter 5 of Integrated Management and Safe Disposal of Solid Waste in Least Developed Asian Countries: A Feasibility Study. 135-228.
- Alamin, M., & Hasan, K. M. (2013). Life Cycle Assessment of Solid Wastes in a University Campus in Bangladesh. *Proceedings of the WasteSafe 2013-3rd Int.Con. on Solid Waste Management in South Asian Countries*. Khulna, Bangladesh.
- Ammasi, R., Victor, J. S., Chellan, R., & Chellappa, M. (2019). Amino Acid Enriched Proteinous Wastes: Recovery and Reuse. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*.
- BBS. (2011). *District Statistics 2011, Khulna*. BANGLADESH BUREAU OF STATISTICS, Statistics Division, Ministry of Planning, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

- Colombo, P., Brusatin, G., Bernardo, E., & Scarinci, G. (2003). Inertization and reuse of waste materials by vitrification and fabrication of glass-based products. *Current Opinion in Solid State and Materials Science*, 225-239.
- Ikechukwu, G. A., & IAENG, M. (2013). Design and Characterization of a Model Polythene. *World Congress on Engineering*, 1-6.
- Islam, M. S., & Moniruzzam, S. M. (2019). Simulation of sustainable solid waste management system in Khulna city. *Sustainable environmental research*.
- KCC. (2017). *Waste Management development project of Khulna City Corporation*. Khulna City Corporation.
- Mansour, A., & Mansour, H. (2015). Reusing waste plastic bottles as an alternative sustainable building material. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 70-85.
- Murtaza, G. (2002). Solid Waste management in Khulna City. *PLAN PLUS, A Journal of Planning, Development, Urbanization & Environment*, 1, 6-15.
- Rajput, D., Bhagade, S., Raut, S., Ralegaonkar, R., & Mandavgane, S. A. (2012). Reuse of cotton and recycle paper mill waste as building material. *Construction and Building Materials*, 470-475.
- RemoveandReplace. (2015). *36 Recycled Scrap Metal Into Furniture Project Ideas*. Retrieved from RemoveandReplace.com: https://removeandreplace.com/2014/05/06/36-scrap-metal-into-furniture-project-ideas/?fbclid=IwAR15Frqny_5wUWv1zeVeE-jVHml1C4nU_421dDcYn_fGTaleMOpF1MejTUA
- Tchobanoglous, G., Hilary, T., & Samuel, V. (1993). *Integrated Solid Waste Management: Engineering Principles and Management Issues*.